

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 1E

Models, simulations, and related software (including pre and post processing and visualization codes)

<https://zenodo.org/records/11122224>

A Versatile Visualization Tool for Exploring NASA Datasets

Micah Acinapura

Contact: macinapura@amnh.org, support@openspaceproject.com

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Solar System

Open Source, Open Architecture, Open Data

OpenSpace

Datasets from PDS, JPL and beyond

From laptop screen to planetarium or display wall

Milky Way

Data in context

Partnership with NASA centers

Worldwide user base

Extra Galactic

NASA's Planetary Spectrum Generator

Gerónimo Villanueva

Associate Director, Solar System Exploration Division
NASA Goddard Space Flight Center
geronimo.Villanueva@nasa.gov

PSG co-authors: **Liuzzi, Faggi, Protopapa, Kofman, Fauchez, Stone, Mandell**

<https://zenodo.org/records/11093251>

The Planetary Spectrum Generator (PSG) is an advanced software for synthesizing and retrieving planetary spectra (atmospheres and surfaces) for a broad range of wavelengths from any observatory, any orbiter, or any lander. PSG integrates several state-of-the-art radiative transfer, orbital, computational and planetary modules, that make use of advanced spectroscopic, climatological and spacecraft databases. In 2022, PSG was selected as Goddard's nominee for NASA's Inventions and Contributions Board (ICB) Software of the Year (SOY) award. This recognition highlights the relevant contributions that this software makes towards new scientific discoveries and to the advancement of space exploration. Importantly, this distinction further motivates the team to continue the prime objective of providing state-of-the-art spectroscopic modeling to the public in a fully open and free manner. That year, PSG also became NASA's most visited site with multiple views (>20 views/visit), demonstrating the great need of the public for such capabilities. Development, maintenance and user assistance are supported by volunteering and discretionary funding. Long-term support of NASA software assets remains a challenge.

PSG is **NASA's planetary spectroscopy tool** that allows to simulate and interpret data from any camera, spectrometer, or spacecraft instrument:

- *Widely used worldwide (1.3 million hits last year)*
- *Fully free and accessible via a friendly web interface, an API framework and an installable Docker virtualization system.*
- *Goddard's Software of the Year 2022*

Extensive user support: Free spectroscopy textbook, extensive online documentation, github repository, tutorial videos, and a thriving support community

Development, maintenance and user assistance are supported by volunteering and discretionary funding.

Long-term support of NASA software assets remains a challenge.

Open Level 2 Greenhouse Gas Algorithm Tools

Peter Somkuti – peter.somkuti@nasa.gov

ESSIC / 610.1

Open Level 2 Greenhouse Gas Algorithm Tools

peter.somkuti@nasa.gov

Historical and state-of-the-art

Our new tools

We aim to achieve the following

- Performant in production
- Flexibility and ease
- Thorough documentation of software **and** theory
- Tutorials, examples

→ We want to increase engagement with scientists, students

“Open science” is not truly open until reasonably educated scientists can make use of it.

We want to consider users with different levels of familiarity and expertise!

- Allow students to explore and learn
- Experts must be able to make meaningful changes

We focus on 3 main aspects of documentation:

- What is the theory behind the software?
[JupyterBook](#), [Quarto](#)
- What do functions do, how do I use them?
[Documenter.jl](#)
- How do I use this software to do science?
[git repositories](#)

Kamodo: A CCMC Open Source Toolkit for Space Physics Simulation Output

Darren De Zeeuw^{1,2}, Lutz Rastaetter¹,
and the CCMC Team

¹NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, Community Coordinated Modeling Center

²Catholic University of America

Email: darren.dezeeuw@nasa.gov, lutz.rastaetter-1@nasa.gov

Kamodo

- Open Source Python project on GitHub
- Access, interpolation, and visualization of space weather models
- Unit conversions, coordinate transformations
- Satellite flythrough extraction
- Core package in PyHC
- Dynamic interactive visualizations

Kamodo

Test of interpolation on coordinate transformed positions.
GITM, GEO Coordinates, 2013/03/16, Slice at: 12.0 hrs 500.0 km Altitude

OceanWATERS = Ocean World Autonomy Testbed for Exploration Research and Simulation

Open-source software for developing and testing autonomy for a simulated Europa lander

Presented by K. Michael Dalal, KBR Inc. at NASA Ames Research Center
(michael.dalal@nasa.gov)

Software: github.com/nasa/ow_simulator

<https://zenodo.org/records/11118299>

- Ocean worlds (e.g. Europa and Enceladus) are prime destinations in the search for signs of extraterrestrial life.
- Robotic missions to distant worlds need to be highly autonomous, e.g. due to communication lag, harsh conditions.
- Autonomy technologies have been rapidly advancing in recent years, e.g. machine learning, generative AI.
- Autonomy technologies are in development at many non-NASA institutions, e.g. universities and companies.
- OceanWATERS was developed at NASA Ames Research Center from late 2018 to present.
 - Funded by the Planetary Exploration Science Technology Office (PESTO) within SMD.
 - Provides visual and physical simulation of a lander on Jupiter's moon Europa.
 - Provides interface for external autonomy software to interact with simulation.
 - Entirely open source at github.com/nasa/ow_simulator
- Research and development using OceanWATERS was solicited by two SMD programs.
 - ARROW : Autonomous Robotics Research for Ocean Worlds (2020-2023).
 - COLDTech : Concepts for Ocean Worlds Life Detection Technology (2021-2024).
- Collectively, 6 research teams in these programs developed and demonstrated potential mission autonomy.
 - Publications are listed at github.com/nasa/ow_simulator/wiki/Bibliography

Recent Upgrades to the Global Reference Atmospheric Model (GRAM) Suite

Soumyo Dutta

Project Manager
Atmospheric Flight and Entry Systems Branch
Langley Research Center
Soumyo.Dutta@nasa.gov

Hilary L. Justh

Planetary Atmosphere Specialist
Natural Environments Branch (EV44)
NASA Marshall Space Flight Center
Hilary.L.Justh@nasa.gov

NASA Langley Research Center
Code Architect
Jim Hoffman
Analytical Mechanics Associates

Planetary Scientist
Kunio Sayanagi

Outer Planet GRAM Developer
Justin Garland
Analytical Mechanics Associates

NASA Marshall Space Flight Center
Earth-GRAM Developer
Patrick White

Data Implementation
Paul Bremner

Corey Walker
Jacobs Space Exploration Group

GRAM Developer
Lee Burns
Jacobs Space Exploration Group

2024 Software for the NASA SMD Workshop
May 8, 2024

GRAM Suite Overview

Engineering-oriented atmospheric model that estimates mean values and statistical variations of atmospheric properties for numerous planetary destinations

- Currently available for Venus, Earth, Mars, Jupiter, Titan, Uranus, and Neptune
- Outputs include atmospheric density, temperature, pressure, chemical composition, radiative fluxes (for Mars-GRAM), and wind components along a user-defined path
- Includes seasonal, diurnal, geographic, and altitude variations when such data are available
- Widely used by engineering community due to ability to create realistic atmospheric dispersions
- Can be integrated into high fidelity flight dynamic simulations of launch, entry, descent and landing (EDL), aerobraking and aerocapture
- Application Program Interface (API) available for Python and soon MATLAB
- GRAM Suite Version 2.0.0 (Released November 2023) included:
 - Addition of Python API and Earth-GRAM Modern Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2 (MERRA-2) Update
- GRAM Suite Spring 2024 release will include:
 - Earth-GRAM gridded forecast upgrade, Mars-GRAM topography data upgrade, Venus-GRAM gravity data upgrade, Uranus-GRAM input model data upgrade
- Available through the NASA Software Catalog <https://software.nasa.gov/software/MFS-33888-1>

(Not, yet, ready for the satellite data deluge)

← <http://rapid-hub.org>
<https://github.com/c-h-david/rapid>
<https://hub.docker.com/r/chdavid/rapid>

Routing Application for Parallel
 computation of Discharge (RAPID)

A Community River Model for Earth- Orbiting Satellites

Cédric H. David

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of
 Technology

Jet Propulsion Laboratory
 California Institute of Technology

Reviewed and determined not to contain Controlled Unclassified
 Information (CUI)

RAPID

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.593867](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.593867)

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docker images

GitHub Actions CI **passing**

GitHub Actions CD **passing**

TAG

[latest](#)

Last pushed 2 months ago by [chdavid](#)

```
docker pull chdavid/rapid:latest
```

Copy

Digest	OS/ARCH	Compressed Size
c3b7c1e3dece	linux/amd64	454.47 MB
fc89164af67a	linux/arm64	445.46 MB

Open Science Highlights

- BSD 3-Clause
- GitHub
- CI/CD with GitHub Actions
- Docker (multi-arch)
- Open Software
- Open Datasets
- Open Publications
- Open Methods

Research driven w/ power Users

- Inspired NOAA National Water Model
- Operational at US Army Corps in support of global operations
- Operational at European Center for Medium Range Weather Forecasting

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Global patterns in river water storage dependent on residence time

Elyssa L. Collins , Cédric H. David , Ryan Riggs, George H. Allen, Tamlin M. Pavelsky, Peirong Lin, Ming Pan, Dai Yamazaki, Ross K. Meentemeyer & Georgina M. Sanchez

[Nature Geoscience](#) (2024) | [Cite this article](#)

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Data availability

Global river discharge and water storage data ('MeanDRS') are made publicly available via Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8248069> (ref. ²⁴). We follow the guidelines (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10161527>) of NASA's Transform to Open Science (TOPS) mission for our open science practices.

Code availability

Our software is publicly available via Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3236649> (ref. ²⁵) and via GitHub at <https://github.com/c-h-david/rrr> (ref. ²⁶). We follow the guidelines (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10161527>) of NASA's Transform to Open Science (TOPS) mission for our open science practices.

US Army Corps of Engineers®

Sustainability needs to thrive during satellite river data deluge:

- Advance information sharing
 - Standard User Documentation / Communication Channels
- Support community
 - Governance / Contributing / Rules / Roles / Engagement / Expectations
- Sustain software lifecycle
 - Streamlined tests / PR templates / Format & Style check